

How Does ChatGPT Measure City Similarities?

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Summary

This paper quantifies GPT's perceptions of cities by converting the descriptive texts, which are responses from GPT using prompts of different word lengths, into numeric embeddings using the BERT model. Our findings reveal that as the prompted length of the response increases, the stability and reliability of GPT's textual descriptions of cities increases. Additionally, when comparing our results with previous studies that utilised Street View images to quantify city similarity, we find that the GPT model effectively links cities with similar characteristics, such as geographical proximity and cultural similarity.

KEYWORDS: City similarity, Generative AI models, GPT

1. Introduction

We seek to answer whether Generative AI, specifically GPT, can serve as a promising tool for linking similar cities based on the city descriptions it generates. Considering GPT's sensitivity to prompts, we explore whether the required length of the response affects the stability of GPT's city descriptions. Additionally, given the extensive debate on the reliability and meaningfulness of GPT's responses, we compare GPT's descriptions with Wikipedia's introductions of selected cities, where the Wikipedia text is considered to broadly reflect social knowledge (Jang *et al.*, 2024). We further compare the city similarity calculated based on GPT's descriptions with previous studies that used Street View images, focusing on the specific city features highlighted by each method and analysing how these features contribute to the perceived city similarity.

2. Data and Methods

2.1. Data Construction

To better enable comparison between GPT's descriptions of cities and previous approaches that have used Street View images, we first compile a list of 23 major global cities, incorporating cities studied by both Zhao *et al.* (2021) and Zhou *et al.* (2014), as shown in Table 1.

We utilise GPT-3.5-turbo (henceforth referred to as GPT) to generate and document descriptions of various cities by GPT. To verify the reliability and validity of GPT's city descriptions and the subsequent city similarity results, we compare them with the similarity results calculated using Street View images from the studies by Zhao *et al.* (2021) and Zhou *et al.* (2014). Considering that Wikipedia is regarded as a (broadly) factual crowdsourcing platform, reflecting general agreement from multiple contributors, and has previously been used to validate GPT's assessment of cities' place identity in alignment with their real-world characteristics (Jang *et al.*, 2024), we also collect the paragraphs of Wikipedia descriptions for the 23 cities mentioned above as the baseline dataset for this study.

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Table 1 The full list of cities analysed in this study

City Name	Country	City Name	Country
Toronto	Canada	Shanghai	China
Montreal	Canada	Hong Kong	China
New York	United States	Tokyo	Japan
London	United Kingdom	Sydney	Australia
Paris	France	Amsterdam	Netherlands
Beijing	China	Zurich	Switzerland
Prague	Czechia	Boston	United States
Berlin	Germany	San Francisco	United States
Vienna	Austria	Seoul	South Korea
Barcelona	Spain	Bangkok	Thailand
Singapore	Singapore	Kuala Lumpur	Malaysia
New Delhi	India		

2.2. Methods

2.2.1 Measuring GPT’s Stability of Perceiving Cities

For each city C_k (where $k = 1, 2, \dots, 23$), 100 responses were generated for each word length (20, 50, 100, 150, 300, 500 and 600 words). The similarity score $S_{k,ij}$ is then calculated between every pair of responses, where i and j represent the indices of two distinct responses for the same city ($i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, 100\}$ and $i < j$). For each city, we compute the variance, $Var(S_k)$, of the similarity scores, which are used to assess the stability of the 100 responses generated from the same prompts.

2.2.2 Analysing GPT’s City Descriptions in Comparison to Wikipedia’s Descriptions

GPT’s descriptions of cities at various prompt lengths and Wikipedia’s descriptions of the same cities are transformed into vectors using the Sentence-BERT model, after which we compute the Spearman correlation coefficient, r_s , between the vectors of two datasets to assess the consistency of information according to the equation (1),

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)} \quad (1)$$

where d_i represents the difference between the ranks of corresponding variables (elements of two vectors in this case), and n is the number of data points (the length of the vector).

2.2.3 Comparing GPT’s City Similarity with Street View Approaches.

We evaluate the correlation between the similarity matrix generated by GPT and that determined in a previous study using Street View imagery (Zhao *et al.*, 2021), focusing on the same 10 cities. To measure the correlation between matrices, we employ the Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), proposed by Wang *et al.* (2004).

2.2.4 Explaining the Discrepancies and Consistencies between GPT-generated City Similarity and Street View Methods.

To further understand the discrepancies and consistencies between the city similarities depicted by GPT and those by Zhao *et al.* (2021), we employ the following methods to analyse which specific city characteristics GPT focuses on when determining the highest similarity between city pairs. The details are shown in Figure 1. Specifically, we segment the paragraphs into sentences and use the Sentence-BERT model to convert these sentences into vectors. We calculate the cosine similarity between sentences and apply the Louvain Community Detection algorithm to group highly similar sentences into clusters. Subsequently, we identify the most similar cluster pairs between cities and employ Latent Dirichlet Allocation to extract key themes from these clusters.

Figure 1 Workflow illustrating the process of identifying the city characteristics GPT focuses on when determining the highest similarity between city pairs.

In the study by Zhou *et al.* (2014), they found that geographic distance also plays a role in city similarity. To examine whether the city similarity depicted by GPT is influenced by geographic distance, we compare our results with the same 21 cities used in that previous study. We use the Sentence-BERT model again to calculate the average similarity between cities after 100 responses and measure the central distance between each city to assess the correlation between the two.

3. Results

3.1. Stability Score of ChatGPT’s Responses

Figure 2 underscores an obvious trend in the stability of responses generated by GPT: as the prompt word length increases, the instability of responses, as measured by variance, although the decrease of the variance plateaus at about 100 words.

Figure 2 Variance of similarity scores across 100 iterations based on descriptions using 20, 50, 100, 150, 300, 500 and 600 words.

3.2. Reliability of GPT’s Responses

The results in Figure 3 illustrate that shorter prompts (e.g., 20 and 50 words) exhibit lower mean correlations, suggesting that shorter GPT-generated descriptions have lower consistency with Wikipedia introductions. Conversely, as the description length increases (e.g., 500 and 600 words), the distribution of the correlation values becomes more concentrated around higher means, indicating

increased consistency.

Figure 3. Distribution of Spearman correlation coefficients between Wikipedia and GPT descriptions at various prompt lengths for 100 repetitions.

3.3. Assessing the Similarity Scores Generated by GPT through Comparison

Our subsequent analysis focuses solely on city description text sets generated using 500 and 600 words. In this section, we examine the similarity between cities based on GPT’s descriptions, comparing it to the city similarities identified by previous studies, specifically those employing Street View image data by Zhao *et al.* (2021) and Zhou *et al.* (2014).

Figure 4 (left) shows city similarities based on Street View data (from Zhao *et al.* (2021)), while Figure 4 (right) presents city similarities derived from GPT-generated descriptions. We calculate the SSIM for Figure 4 (left) and the lower-left (600 words) and upper-right(500 words) matrices of Figure 4 (right) respectively, yielding values of 0.1933 and 0.1963, respectively.

We segment the GPT-generated paragraph responses into individual sentences, cluster semantically similar sentences into groups, and recalculate the similarity scores for each city pair within each cluster. Using GPT responses of 500-word and 600-word, the results are presented in Figures 5 and 6. To further interpret which characteristics GPT emphasises in its descriptions that contribute to city pair similarity, we focus on the cluster group corresponding to the highest similarity score for each city pair (as annotated in Figures 4 and 5). We apply topic modelling using LDA to identify the specific features highlighted by GPT in these clusters, and the results are shown in Figures 7 and 8.

Upon comparing similarity scores based on the 500-word descriptions with the results obtained using Street View images by Zhao *et al.* (2021), we observe partial consistency. Both methods identify high similarities between certain city pairs, but the reasons for these similarities differ. Differences also emerged in other cases, likely due to the different city aspects each method focused on. When comparing the results of the 600-word descriptions with Street View image outcomes, we find that the similarity scores were consistent with those from the 500-word descriptions, yet the reasons for the similarities between cities may have shifted with more detailed descriptions by GPT based on Figures 7 and 8.

Figure 4 City similarity scores recalculated based on Zhao *et al.* (2021)'s work (left) and those calculated using GPT (right), with the lower-left matrix from 600-word descriptions and the upper-right matrix from 500-word descriptions.

Figure 5 Range of city pair similarity scores based on clustered sentences (500-word descriptions).

Figure 6 Range of city pair similarity scores based on clustered sentences (600-word descriptions).

	Left City Topics	Right City Topics
Beijing - Hong Kong	art, museum, chinese, city, gallery	city, temple, museum, cultural, art
Beijing - London	city, street, food, cuisine, market	market, city, street, food, cuisine
Beijing - Montreal	city, street, food, cuisine, market	city, food, scene, cuisine, french
Beijing - New York	art, museum, chinese, city, gallery	museum, art, city, theater, world
Beijing - Paris	art, museum, chinese, city, gallery	museum, art, louvre, home, mona
Beijing - Shanghai	city, street, food, cuisine, market	city, food, scene, culinary, scene
Beijing - Sydney	art, museum, chinese, city, gallery	art, opera, house, museum, gallery
Beijing - Tokyo	city, modern, history, ancient, china	city, bustling, japan, tradition, vibrant
Beijing - Toronto	city, street, food, cuisine, market	city, food, scene, cuisine, street
Hong Kong - London	city, temple, museum, cultural, art	museum, art, gallery, city, theater
Hong Kong - Montreal	market, street, city, food, cuisine	city, food, scene, cuisine, french
Hong Kong - New York	city, temple, museum, cultural, art	museum, art, city, theater, world
Hong Kong - Paris	city, temple, museum, cultural, art	museum, art, louvre, home, mona
Hong Kong - Shanghai	city, skyline, skyscraper, towering, stunning	city, tower, skyline, building, skyscraper
Hong Kong - Sydney	market, street, city, food, cuisine	city, offer, diverse, food, market
Hong Kong - Tokyo	market, street, city, food, cuisine	city, food, shopping, street, district
Hong Kong - Toronto	city, skyline, skyscraper, towering, stunning	city, tower, ch, iconic, skyline
London - Montreal	market, city, street, food, cuisine	city, food, scene, cuisine, french
London - New York	museum, art, gallery, city, theater	museum, art, city, theater, world
London - Paris	museum, art, gallery, city, theater	museum, art, louvre, home, mona
London - Shanghai	museum, art, gallery, city, theater	art, museum, chinese, city, gallery
London - Sydney	market, city, street, food, cuisine	city, offer, diverse, food, market
London - Tokyo	city, history, culture, vibrant, diverse	city, bustling, japan, tradition, vibrant
London - Toronto	market, city, street, food, cuisine	city, food, scene, cuisine, street
Montreal - New York	city, food, scene, cuisine, french	city, food, cuisine, restaurant, culinary
Montreal - Paris	city, food, scene, cuisine, french	city, cuisine, culinary, restaurant, michelinstarred
Montreal - Shanghai	city, food, scene, cuisine, french	city, food, cuisine, culinary, scene
Montreal - Sydney	city, food, scene, cuisine, french	city, offer, diverse, food, market
Montreal - Tokyo	city, food, scene, cuisine, french	city, food, shopping, street, district
Montreal - Toronto	city, food, scene, cuisine, french	city, food, scene, cuisine, street
New York - Paris	city, food, cuisine, restaurant, culinary	city, cuisine, culinary, restaurant, michelinstarred
New York - Shanghai	city, food, cuisine, restaurant, culinary	city, food, cuisine, culinary, scene
New York - Sydney	museum, art, city, theater, world	art, opera, house, museum, gallery
New York - Tokyo	city, culture, people, diverse, vibrant	city, bustling, japan, tradition, vibrant
New York - Toronto	city, food, cuisine, restaurant, culinary	city, food, scene, cuisine, street
Paris - Shanghai	city, cuisine, culinary, restaurant, michelinstarred	city, food, cuisine, culinary, scene
Paris - Sydney	museum, art, louvre, home, mona	art, opera, house, museum, gallery
Paris - Tokyo	city, history, culture, vibrant, light	city, bustling, japan, tradition, vibrant
Paris - Toronto	city, cuisine, culinary, restaurant, michelinstarred	city, food, scene, cuisine, street
Shanghai - Sydney	shopping, boutique, street, city, market	city, offer, diverse, food, market
Shanghai - Tokyo	city, tower, skyline, building, skyscraper	city, bustling, japan, tradition, vibrant
Shanghai - Toronto	city, food, scene, cuisine, french	city, food, scene, cuisine, street
Sydney - Tokyo	city, offer, diverse, food, market	city, food, shopping, street, district
Sydney - Toronto	city, offer, diverse, food, market	city, food, scene, cuisine, street
Tokyo - Toronto	city, food, shopping, street, district	city, food, scene, cuisine, street

Figure 7 The topics of city pairs (500-word descriptions).

	Left City Topics	Right City Topics
Beijing - Hong Kong	city, street, food, cuisine, visitor	food, city, cuisine, sum, dim
Beijing - London	city, modern, ancient, history, china	city, history, culture, vibrant, diverse
Beijing - Montreal	art, museum, gallery, chinese, city	festival, art, city, museum, scene
Beijing - New York	city, modern, ancient, history, china	city, culture, diverse, vibrant, people
Beijing - Paris	city, street, food, cuisine, visitor	cuisine, city, restaurant, culinary, french
Beijing - Shanghai	city, street, food, cuisine, visitor	city, shopping, street, food, cuisine
Beijing - Sydney	art, museum, gallery, chinese, city	art, museum, gallery, cultural, city
Beijing - Tokyo	city, street, food, cuisine, visitor	food, city, market, culinary, street
Beijing - Toronto	city, street, food, cuisine, visitor	city, food, market, scene, diverse
Hong Kong - London	food, city, cuisine, sum, dim	market, street, city, food, cuisine
Hong Kong - Montreal	food, city, cuisine, sum, dim	city, food, scene, cuisine, culinary
Hong Kong - New York	city, skyline, building, international, home	financial, street, wall, city, world
Hong Kong - Paris	market, street, shopping, city, bustling	city, boutique, marais, fashion, street
Hong Kong - Shanghai	food, city, cuisine, sum, dim	city, shopping, street, food, cuisine
Hong Kong - Sydney	food, city, cuisine, sum, dim	city, food, market, dining, scene
Hong Kong - Tokyo	food, city, cuisine, sum, dim	food, city, market, culinary, street
Hong Kong - Toronto	city, skyline, building, international, home	tower, city, cn, skyline, view
London - Montreal	museum, art, gallery, city, theater	festival, art, city, museum, scene
London - New York	museum, art, gallery, city, theater	museum, art, theater, city, broadway
London - Paris	market, street, city, food, cuisine	cuisine, city, restaurant, culinary, french
London - Shanghai	museum, art, gallery, city, theater	art, museum, chinese, city, gallery
London - Sydney	city, history, culture, vibrant, diverse	art, museum, gallery, cultural, city
London - Tokyo	park, city, hyde, green, space	city, tradition, japan, bustling, vibrant
London - Toronto	city, cultural, vibrant, reflected, diversity	city, park, offer, island, green
Montreal - New York	city, cultural, vibrant, reflected, diversity	city, culture, diverse, vibrant, people
Montreal - Paris	city, food, scene, cuisine, culinary	cuisine, city, restaurant, culinary, french
Montreal - Shanghai	festival, art, city, museum, scene	art, museum, chinese, city, gallery
Montreal - Sydney	festival, art, city, museum, scene	art, museum, gallery, cultural, city
Montreal - Tokyo	city, cultural, vibrant, reflected, diversity	food, city, market, culinary, street
Montreal - Toronto	festival, art, city, museum, scene	art, city, ontario, museum, gallery
New York - Paris	city, culture, diverse, vibrant, people	cuisine, city, restaurant, culinary, french
New York - Shanghai	museum, art, theater, city, broadway	art, museum, chinese, city, gallery
New York - Sydney	museum, art, theater, city, broadway	art, museum, gallery, cultural, city
New York - Tokyo	city, culture, diverse, vibrant, people	city, tradition, japan, bustling, vibrant
New York - Toronto	city, culture, diverse, vibrant, people	city, food, market, scene, diverse
Paris - Shanghai	cuisine, city, restaurant, culinary, french	city, shopping, street, food, cuisine
Paris - Sydney	art, museum, louvre, home, work	art, museum, gallery, cultural, city
Paris - Tokyo	cuisine, city, restaurant, culinary, french	food, city, market, culinary, street
Paris - Toronto	cuisine, city, restaurant, culinary, french	city, food, market, scene, diverse
Shanghai - Sydney	art, museum, chinese, city, gallery	art, museum, gallery, cultural, city
Shanghai - Tokyo	city, shopping, street, food, cuisine	food, city, market, culinary, street
Shanghai - Toronto	art, museum, chinese, city, gallery	art, city, ontario, museum, gallery
Sydney - Tokyo	city, vibrant, offer, australia, natural	city, tradition, japan, bustling, vibrant
Sydney - Toronto	art, museum, gallery, cultural, city	art, city, ontario, museum, gallery
Tokyo - Toronto	food, city, market, culinary, street	city, food, market, scene, diverse

Figure 8 The topics of city pairs (600-word descriptions).

3.4. Relationship between ChatGPT-constructed City Similarity and Geographic Distance

We investigate whether the city similarity depicted by GPT aligns with the established knowledge that geographic distance influences city similarity. Using the average correlation of 100 repeated responses per city pair, the 500-word descriptions and 600-word descriptions both show a moderate negative correlation between city similarity and geodesic distance, with correlation coefficients of -0.508 and -0.473 respectively, both highly statistically significant ($p < 0.01$).

4. Conclusion

This paper examined the stability of GPT in generating city descriptions and the reliability of city similarity results derived from GPT-generated descriptions, suggesting that GPT holds promise as a tool for measuring city similarity.

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Biographies

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Richard Harris is Professor of Quantitative Social Geography at the University of Bristol. He is interested in socio-spatial inequalities within society and their causes, and likes doing things with data and running. Sometimes those interests combine.